

Hybrid Security Model for Identity Management System

Prof. Souley Boukhari¹
Department of Mathematical
Sciences, ATBU, Bauchi,
(Nigeria)

Amatullah Yahaya Aliyu²
Department of Computer Science,
Federal Polytechnic, Bauchi,
(Nigeria)

amatullahya@fptb.edu.ng

Abstract

As technology becomes more readily available to the average computer users, it has become easier to impersonate, therefore it is important that Identity Cards should include at least one security feature that protects them from fraudulent use and duplication. This research developed a secure platform for identity management through combining smart card and biometric technologies (Hybrid) so as to create an equally fraud-free, forge-proof and convenient (no need to remember password) identification in higher institutions of learning. The identity management systems reviewed did not combine biometric and smart technology, therefore were faced with security challenges such as impersonation and fraud. Thus hybrid security model with contactless technology was used to wave security challenges and cut down cost of smart card reader (no need for expensive password administrators). The experimental results showed that in the developed model more than 70% of respondents agreed on the security of the system. Therefore the developed (Hybrid) security model can be used to avoid fraud and impersonation in higher institutions of learning.

Keywords: Security, Data integrity, Verification, Confidentiality, Privacy, Authentication, Impersonation, cryptography.

1. BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Presently, Nigeria is critically facing security challenges because people are not uniquely identified and tagged. The situation led to insecurity in Nigeria with different trends and dimensions from one geopolitical zone to the other and various faceless activities such as sect called Boko Haram in the North, rampant armed robbery in the South-West, notorious robbery and kidnapping in the South-East and South-South, and our educational environment are not exempted (Johnson, 2013).

Stevens in BBC News (2006) commented on the need to enforce the use of uniquely identity cards, stressed they have benefits in tackling serious crimes, such as identity theft. In order to compliment the federal government of Nigeria's effort to improve access and the quality of

education in the country, the need to provide the nation with a genuine and common identification system for students and staff of various tertiary institutions is paramount. This will be an effective solution to the problems of declining standards and values in the country's tertiary institutions.

Identity management (or ID management, or simply IdM) is a broad administrative area that deals with identifying individuals in a system (such as a country, a network, or an organization) and controlling access to the resources in that system by placing restrictions on the established identities of the individuals (Terri, 2014). From universities to primary schools, a revolution in technology is taking shape. Twenty-first-century innovation is bringing automation and improved security to school campuses worldwide with school security systems. With education costs skyrocketing, departments at all levels are looking for ways to do more with less, trimming expenses while maximizing staff productivity. Add the looming threats to campus security, and educators must make decisions that balance quality of education with protecting the safety of their students and staff. The same technology that corporations use for access control system can be used to improve school campus security as well. Educational campuses can realize a wide range of benefits, from tightening security, to streamlining admissions, to improving paid services with these types of ID card technologies like secure smart ID cards embedded with "smart" features such as biometric identification.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

According to Muhammad (2013), Institutions of higher education campuses in developing countries, especially Nigeria have been slow to adopt technologies commonly used in the private business sector. The access card technologies like Barcode, Radio Frequency Identification, (RFID) magnetic stripe, smart card, and graphics photo security features are used to streamline their operations.

According to Robin (2011), on a report conducted in sixteen West African countries, Nigeria inclusive, 52 percent of faculties said their institutions fail to dedicate sufficient resources to campus safety and security.

Based on the present identity management system of Federal Polytechnic Bauchi, Plastic Identity Cards are the usual form of identification. These are produced using ready special card printers. The cards are designed in graphic design software like Corel Draw and printed using ready special card printer without security feature like magnetic stripe, smart card,

graphics and biometric security features, these results to high cases of fraud and card forgery in the institution.

Some scholars such as Shoewu et. al (2011), Shehu and Dika (2011) and Kadry and Smaili (2010) attempted electronic identity management system and were faced with challenges such as not able to eliminate the risk of impersonation, lacking the ability to identify each student present in class thereby providing a lower recognition rate (facial images) which are subject to change between the time of enrolment and time of verification therefore does not offer any privacy protection and also poses a bigger financial burden during installation.

In all as reported by Khan et. al (2010) combining smartcard and biometric (finger print) technology may be more secured and convenient in terms of operation, hence this serves as motivation. Therefore there is need to combine smart and biometric (fingerprint) technology in order to yield a better result.

1.3 Aim and Objectives

The aim is to develop a hybrid security model for Identity Management System using smart card (contactless Radio Frequency Identification technology) and fingerprint technology so as to streamline campus activities, to dedicate sufficient resources to campus safety and security in order to prevent high cases of fraud and card forgery in the institution.

The objectives are to:

1. Develop a secure framework for identity management and control through the use of Biometric and smart card technology.
2. Analyze and develop a user application identity management system.
3. Integrate objectives one (1) and two (2) above.

Evaluate the Framework based on security as a performance metric against Shoewu et al (2011); Shehu and Dika (2011) and Kadry and Smaili (2010).

2. REVIEWS ON IDENTITY MANAGEMENT AND CONTROL

Bali (2009) notes that the objective of a national ID card is to provide a universal government-issued document that validates an individual's identity and that can then be used for purposes of identification in various functions. In the contribution of (Okoli, 2010), the National Identification system is needed in many governments sectors for an effective application and execution of their governmental policies and programs.

It is clearly enshrined in the national constitution that the security and welfare of all the people or citizens in Nigeria shall be the primary purpose of all the tiers of government Federal Republic of Nigeria. Secondly, in the case of education, the national policy on education, gratifyingly, adopts education in Nigeria, as an instrument par excellence for effecting national development. It specifically states the categorical levels of education to include the primary, secondary and tertiary. The tertiary level is the highest level (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999).

The implication of all the above is that since the highest level of manpower development and capacity building in Nigeria, is done at the tertiary education level, the effective and efficient management and identity management of the human are material resources of all the tertiary educational institutions which will definitely and surely enhance national security in the country (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2004).

Beynon-Davies (2007) notes, in the Information Society an individual may take on a number of different identities. One for each electronic service in the public, private and voluntary sectors with which the individual engages. As a consequence, an individual may accumulate a vast array of personal identifiers for such “services” also likely to accrue a range of physical representations or tokens of such multiple identification as in credit card, debit card, driving license, passport, library card, and parking permit. The need to have several identities can suggest the possibility of identification fraud of individuals and organizations in contemporary life.

2.1.1 Identity Cards and Tagging System

An identity document is any document which may be used to verify aspects of a person's personal identity. If issued in the form of a small, mostly standard-sized card, it is usually called an identity card (Maltoni and Cappelli, 2008).

The Napoleonic identity card was the main basis of all modern ID systems. Its main purpose was to hold down wages, by stopping workers moving around to find better jobs and higher wages (Nathan, 2009).

Back during the American Civil War, identification tags were not issued or required. However, the thought of identification was undoubtedly on the minds of the soldiers. Prior to the battle many soldiers would write their name on a piece of paper and attach it to their shirt or etch their names in a piece of wood, bore a hole through it and then put it on a string around their neck. In those days soldiers that fell on the battlefield were buried almost where

they fell. Many soldiers did not want to fall into that 'Unknown' category. The Nigerian government had yet to implement a plan for identification meanwhile; those in the commercial industry were well ahead of the curve. They offered 'soldier identification tags' in their magazines and sent their representatives into the field to sell them. Even though there was a conscious effort by soldiers to ensure identification; when the war ended in 1865 around 42% of the fallen soldiers were buried as 'Unknown' (Williams, 2010).

Organizations with large number of members go through hectic processes in verifying and adequately managing their members' record, which are usually in paper kept in files cabinet and finding an employee data usually takes hours of search. Going by the experience of best practices such as the United States of America, United Kingdom, Germany, China, Kenya and South Africa, in the mid- to late 1990s and early 2000s, schools across the United States implemented the requirement that students must wear ID badges in order to be identified as enrolled students. This requirement has been put in place in the wake of tragedies in different schools in which shootings and other violent crimes occurred. ID badges are now part of the norm for many students. Some schools have even hired security guards to check book bags and other personal belongings as students enter the building (Cycom, 2006).

Schools around the nation have invested in the security of their students, faculty, and staff. They have purchased ID card printers in order to produce the ID badges on site. ID card printers and ID card holders are two necessary items needed for the safety of the students and employees. Many schools supply ID card holders and lanyards so that the ID badges could be worn securely around the neck. Every student, faculty member, and staff of these schools has to wear an ID badge on a daily basis. In some cases, students are punished for not wearing their badges. When everyone in the school wears an ID badge, they are all easily identified as being affiliated with the school somehow, whether as a student or employee. Outsiders stand out because they do not have proper identification. If they do not belong in the school, they are escorted out, and sometimes law enforcement is called for assistance when necessary (Kenzie, 2011).

2.1.2 Need for Secure Identity Cards.

As technology becomes more readily available to the average computer user, it has become easier to duplicate and create forged ID cards. That's why it is important that your ID cards include at least one security feature that protects them from fraudulent use and duplication, (Terri, 2014).

The Electronic Identity Card (EIC) is a polycarbonate smart card equipped with a microchip (supporting cryptographic functions), and a laser band (featuring an embedded hologram). It contains personal (e.g. name, surname, date of birth) and biometric data (photo and fingerprint) of a citizen (Franco et. al 2014).

In the present era of Information Technology, transmission of information in a secured manner is the primary concern of all agencies; therefore security is highly essential as intruders are very keen to rob the information with all their might and intelligence (Mallick et. al 2011).

According to Johnson (2013) generating a secure and credible information database of all students would be useful as an instrument to create an equally fraud-free and forge-proof identification for students and staff of institutions. The overall intention is to reduce the problems of impersonation, cultism, theft, lost transcripts and other vices prevalent in higher institutions of learning.

With application of smartcard in identity management, researchers like (Khan et. al 2010; Brian 2017; and Xavier 2017) agreed that combining smartcard and any biometric may have better security and more convenience to users for simple day- to- day actions. While smart card can be convenient when used for door locks and quick pay systems, they have insufficient securities protecting the information they hold (Michael 2016; Hari 2017).

2.2 Reviews on Conceptual Technological Frameworks

2.2.1 *Cryptography and Security Features*

Cryptography is the science of writing in secret code and is an ancient art; the first documented use of cryptography in writing dates back to circa 1900 B.C. when an Egyptian scribe used non-standard hieroglyphs in an inscription.

According to Bellare and Rogaway (2005), Cryptography is the practice and study of hiding information. Modern cryptography intersects the disciplines of mathematics, computer science, and electrical engineering. Applications of cryptography include ATM cards, computer passwords, and electronic commerce. Cryptology prior to the modern age was almost synonymous with encryption, the conversion of information from a readable state to apparent nonsense. The sender retained the ability to decrypt the information and therefore avoid unwanted persons being able to read it.

2.2.2 Encryption and Decryption

When Julius Caesar sent messages to his generals, he didn't trust his Messengers. So he replaced every A in his messages with a D, every B with an E, and so on through the alphabet. Only someone who knew the “shift by 3” rule could decipher his messages. Data that can be read and understood without any special measure is called plaintext or clear text. The method of disguising plaintext in such a way as to hide its substance is called encryption. Encrypting plaintext results in unreadable gibberish called cipher text. You use encryption to ensure that information is hidden from anyone for whom it is not intended, even those who can see the encrypted data. The process of reverting cipher text to its original plaintext is called decryption (Ranjan, 2001), as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Encryption and Decryption (Source: Ranjan, 2001).

2.2.4 Biometric Technology

EPIC (2007), defines the term „BIOMETRICS“ as derived from the Greek words “bio” (life) and “metrics” (to measure). Biometric System has become available over the last few decades, due to significant advances in the field of computer processing.

The integrated biometric verification system smart cards are used to store personal biometric data of a person instead of storing them in a database. If smart cards are correctly authenticated such as with cryptographic signatures, attacks to biometric databases are reduced like template replacement or cross-matching of biometric databases. Furthermore, smart cards are used to match reference data with the actual data of a claimed identity. These systems are called matching-on-card (Karl and Claus, 2011).

To positively prove the legitimate owner of a smart card, biometric user authentication is important. In contrast to passwords, biometric characteristics cannot be stolen or transferred (Robert and Raul, 2009).

2.3 Related Work

Shoewu et. al (2011) attempted an embedded computer based lecture attendance management system where a single-chip computer based subsystems (an improvised electronic card

reader) were interfaced serially to serial port of the digital computer. The electronic card is a model of a smart card containing the student identity (ID-name, Matriculation number and five pin encrypted code).

2.3.1 Strengths of the Lecture Attendance Management System

The system though provided a simplified, low cost embedded computer based system solution to the management of lecture attendance problem.

2.3.2 Weaknesses of the Lecture Attendance Management System

The system is devise-based in which students have to carry RFID cards and also the RFID detectors are needed to be installed. It does not eliminate the problem of impersonation.

Shehu and Dika, (2011) attempted a real time computer vision algorithms in automatic identity management systems using computer vision and face recognition algorithms and integrating both into the process of identification management

2.3.3 Strengths of the Real Time Computer Vision Algorithm

The system eliminates classical student identification such as calling student names, or checking respective identification cards.

2.3.4 Weaknesses of the Real Time Computer Vision Algorithm

The system lacks the ability to identify each student present in class thereby providing a lower recognition rate because facial images are subject to change between the time of enrolment and time of verification and also poses a bigger financial burden during installation and does not offer any privacy protection.

In (Kadry and Smaili, 2010), a wireless identity management system based on Iris recognition was attempted using Daugman's algorithm. The system uses an off-line iris recognition management system.

2.3.5 Strengths of the Wireless Identity Management System

The system can finish all the process including capturing the image of iris recognition, extracting minutiae, storing and matching at the same time.

2.3.6 Weaknesses of the Wireless Identity Management System

3. THE PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed system introduces a new automatic identification management system, which integrates fingerprint authentication and smartcard technology into the process of identification management. The smart card is used with smart card reader and bio-

identification reader such as finger print scanner to automatically verify and secure a person's identity.

It is made up of two processes namely; enrolment and authentication.

4. During enrolment, the personal data and biometric data of user are captured and the minutiae data are extracted and stored in a database as a template along with the user's ID.

It is difficult to lay the transmission lines where topography is bad. It provides a lower recognition rate because iris images are subject to change between the time of enrolment and time of verification, therefore it is not secured.

In all as reported by Khan et. al (2010) combining smartcard and biometric (fingerprint) technology may be more secured and convenience in terms of operation. Hence this is an open problem suggested by Khan et al (2010) to combine and explore the advantages of smart and biometric (fingerprint) technology in identification, therefore this serves as motivation to come up with a hybrid security model, as this may yield a better result.

3.2 Smartcard Subsystem Model

Contactless smart card system is closely related to Contact Smart card system. Like Contact card system, information is stored on a chip embedded within the contactless smart card. However unlike the contact smart card, power supplied to the card as well as the data exchanged between the card and the reader are achieved without the use of contacts but using magnetic or electromagnetic field to both power the card as well as to exchange data with the reader.

The contactless card contains an antenna embedded within the plastic body of the card. The USB cable and the Ethernet cable will be plugged to the smart card reader and to the developing machine, the microcontroller will send request to the developing machine which contains Database server where all the tables reside. The two LEDs on the contactless smart card reader will be powered on leaving red and green light. Once the card is brought into electromagnetic field of the Reader, the chip in the card is powered on. Once the chip is powered on, a wireless communication protocol would be initiated and established between the card and the Reader for data transfer. Database server will send a signer or a bit either zero or one to the developing machine, after some time the red LED stops blinking leaving the green to blink about three to four times and then stops, indicating that the card is registered otherwise not registered.

Figure 2: Smart Card Subsystem Model (Source: smart card Alliance 2012)

3.3 Biometric Subsystem Model

This comprises of three stages namely, the physical representation stage, Measurement stage and Query stage.

1. Physical Representation stage: at this stage, biometric entity such as finger print is scanned into the system.
2. Measurement process: at this stage, the following process can take place:
 - i. Biometric entity is captured as raw image
 - ii. Pre-processing of Raw image is done
 - iii. Raw image extraction is done
 - iv. Creation of template for the raw image, and
 - v. Saving template to the database, this is also called Reference Template
3. Query Stage: At this stage, new biometric entity is scanned, processed and extracted then the template in the Database is compared for matching, if matched, a message will be displayed as valid then authentication will be done and credential is accessed, but if not matched it displays message as invalid and halt, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Biometric Sub system Model (Source: Xavier 2017)

4. RESULT

This study collected data samples by conducting offline survey aiming at universities and polytechnics students as smart card users. Universities and polytechnic students were selected because students are usually among the most informed group of people in the society and aware of use of information technology as shown in table 1.

Table1 shows the percentage and frequency of the responses.

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage of Respondents' Response to the Security Section's Items

Variables	Questions						
			Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
Security	I trust in the technology that smart card system is using	N	6	39	59	212	327
		%	1	6.2	9.1	33.6	51.0
	I am not worried about the security of smart card system	N	6	68	89	252	245
		%	1.0	10.8	10.4	39.4	38.4
	Smart card systems are trustworthy	N	6	14	124	299	196
		%	1.0	2.3	19.4	46.6	30.6
	Security will be important when using smart card	N	6	6	38	218	365
	%	1.0	1.0	6.1	34.6	57.4	
Overall, the smart card system is secure		N	12	10	99	271	245
		%	1.9	1.7	15.5	42.4	38.4
	I feel that message will be transmitted	N	17	36	73	226	288

	correctly from the original to the recipient	%	2.7	5.6	11.4	35.3	45.0
Data integrity	I believe that smart card prevents accidental loss of data and data decay	N	22	30	116	296	174
		%	3.5	4.7	18.2	46.3	27.3
Non-Repudiation	I believe that in smart card if a certain transaction is performed, it never could be denied by party	N	12	38	90	246	251
		%	2.1	6.0	14.1	38.6	39.2
Privacy	I believe that my information is well protected	N	6	43	82	328	180
		%	1	6.8	12.9	51.2	28.1
Verification	I trust in the ability of a smart card system to protect my privacy	N	12	50	80	240	255
		%	2.0	7.9	12.6	37.5	39.9
	I believe that smart card is able to confirm the identity of cardholder before using a card	N	30	32	64	261	254
		%	4.7	5.0	10.0	40.8	39.5
Confidentiality and Authentication	Access to confidential information is strictly by the use of special codes and passwords	N	43	42	110	213	228
		%	6.9	6.6	17.2	33.5	35.8
	Only authorized individuals are able to access to confidential information	N	35	28	101	247	225
		%	5.5	4.4	15.9	38.8	35.3

Regarding the verification of smart card technology, once respondents were asked that smart card is able to confirm the identity of cardholder before using a card, $40.8 + 39.5 = (80.3\%)$ either agree or strongly agree rather than $4.7 + 5 = (9.7\%)$ disagree, hence same working goes to all. Nearly 14% of those responding either disagree or strongly disagree that access to confidential information stored in smart card chip is strictly limited by the use of special codes and passwords while almost 70% agree.

Figure 4. Users' Opinions about Smart Card Security Principles

Hence this shows that more than 70% of respondents recognized smartcard as a secure device,

and the values of those that disagree and strongly disagree, converge to zero, as shown in Figure 4.

1. Test Case 1: Input Data

The screenshot shows a web application window titled "Secure Identity Management System" with a sub-header "Biometric Enrollment". On the left, there are four input fields: "ID Code:" with a "Search" button, "Name:", "RFID Tag:", and "Phone:". To the right of these fields is a large rectangular area for a photo, with a "PHOTO" label at the bottom. On the far right, there are four buttons: "Enrollment", "Save", "Verification", and "Close".

Figure 5: Input Interface Showing Biometric Enrolment

The screenshot shows a web browser window titled "ID-Card" with the URL "localhost/idcardsystem/register_newcard.php?cid=11". The page header features the logo of The Federal Polytechnic Bauchi and the text "The Federal Polytechnic Bauchi Secured Identity Management System". Below the header, there are two tabs: "Unregistered Cards" and "Registered Cards". The main form contains several input fields: "Card Tag No:" (with the value "119202173197213"), "Phone No:", "School:" (a dropdown menu), "Address:" (a text area), "Name:", "Passport:" (with a "Browse..." button and "No file selected." text), and "Department:" (a dropdown menu). At the bottom of the form, there is a "Register Card" button. The Windows taskbar is visible at the bottom of the browser window, showing the time as 11:26 AM on 8/14/2017.

Figure 6: Input Interface Showing Data to be Input

2. Result for Test Case 1:

Figure 7: Output Interface Showing Captured Finger

Figure 8: Output Interface Showing Template for Fingerprint Verification

Figure 9: Output Interface Showing Lost Card Replacement

The system timing for the verification of the three different users using a live scan as seen in Figures 10 to 12, with an average execution time of 0.0416726 seconds, and is equivalent to 0.042 seconds to 3 significant Figures.

Figure 10: System Timing for User 3

Figure 11: System Timing for User 1

Figure 12: System Timing for User 2

5. RECOMMENDATION

The Hybrid model/system is a relative new technology, it is not still integrated in PC, so it is recommended that IT departments need to make a conscious decision before making the purchase and change its structure.

6. CONCLUSION

Conclusively, the developed Hybrid model system would solve security problem associated with the existing system, with the data being processed, verified, and stored over a secured platform, with an effective and efficient Biometric system that will guaranty the authenticity of identity document.

In the evaluation of the developed model, based on the survey conducted in order to measure the level of security in smart card technology and its importance for user acceptance more than 70% of respondents recognized smartcard as a secure device and Pearson correlation shows that the values of the correlation are closed to 1, therefore there is a strong positive correlation between security and all the security principles as security is the main focus of the research work. Hence combining smart and biometric technology automatically verifies, authenticate and secure a person's identity because fingerprints satisfy uniqueness, stability, permanency and easily taking, more than facial images or the use of electronic card only. The prototype of this system has been tested with different forms of data and it is achieved that the system successfully generates a secure platform for identity management that collects data processes data, stores them and also performs the verification test and finally give a status report about the identity.

7. References

- Annu, M. (2006), Identity Management Systems a Comparison of Current Solutions. Helsinki University of Technology, Helsinki, Finland .pp 14- 25
- Bali, V. (2009). Tinkering Toward a National Identification System: An experiment on policy attitudes. *Policy Study journal*,37: pp 233-255.
- BBC News (2006). "UK | UK Politics | ID cards are of 'good value'". BBC News. In http://news.bbc.co.uk/2/hi/uk_news/politics/4659228.stm.
- Beynon-Davies, P. (2007). Personal identity management and electronic government: The case of the national identity card in the UK. *J. Enterprise Information Management*, 20: 244-270.
- Boritz, J. E. (2000). "IS Practitioners' Views on Core Concepts of Information Integrity". *International Journal of Accounting Information Systems*. Elsevier. (Journal No. 02) http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Data_integrity
- Cycom, C. (2006).The History of Cryptography. <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cryptography>.
- Dhaheri, S. (2005). Briefing on the UAE National ID card project, Dubai. pp 50-54
- EPIC- Electronic Privacy Information Centre (2007): „National ID Cards“, <http://www.opic.org/privacy/Idcards/>.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (1999). Decree No 24-the 1999 constitution. Abuja: Government Press
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004).National Policy on Education. Abuja: NERDC
- Franco, A., Mario, C., Andrea, D., and Fabio, F. (2014). The Italian Electronic Identity Card: Overall Architecture and its Infrastructure.
- Hari, J. K. (2017). Smart Card Future Life, 9th Edn.,Course Technology Cengage Learning, Australia, ISBN: 053846951X, pp: 700.
- Jain, A. K., Bolle, R., and Pankanti, S. (2007). Biometrics: Personal Identification in Networked Society. Kluwer Academic Publishers. pp 50.
- John, W. (2003). Multi-Purpose Smart Card for Higher Education Institutions in Africa. pp 60.
- Johnson, R. (2013). Creation of Central National Database in Nigeria: Challenges and Prospects Information and Knowledge Management ISSN 2224-5758 (Paper) ISSN 2224-896X (Online) 3, No.12, 2013.
- Kadry S., and Smaili, M. (2010). Wireless Attendance Management System based on Iris Recognition. *Scientific Research and Essays* 5(12). pp. 1428-1435.

- Katz, J., and Lindell, Y. (2006). "Introduction to Modern Cryptography." http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Digital_signature.
- Karl, K., and Claus, V. (2011). Biometric Hash algorithm for dynamic handwriting embedded on a java card. Copyright © 2014 ACM, Inc.
- Kenzie, W. (2011). Schools Make Students Wear ID Badges. Published. pp 42-45
- Khan, B., Khan, M. K., and Alghathbar, K. S. (2010). Biometrics and identity management for homeland security applications in Saudi Arabia. *Journal of Business Management* 4(15), pp. 3296-3306.
- Maltonsi, D., and Cappelli, R. (2008). Fingerprint Recognition, a Handbook of Biometric, Springer Science. Business Media, U.S.A. pp 44.
- Robert, M., and Raul, S. (2009). An Approach to Biometric Identity Management Using Low-Cost Equipment. Fifth International Conference on Intelligent Information Hiding and Multimedia Signal Processing, Australia.
- Sharat, S. C. (2015). Online Fingerprint Verification System. A M Tech Thesis, Department of Electrical Engineering, Faculty of Graduate School of the University of New York at Buffalo.
- Shehu, V., and Dika, A. (2011). Using Real Time Computer Vision Algorithms in Automatic identity Management Systems. Proceedings of the ITI 2010 32nd Int. conf. on Information Technology Interfaces, New York.
- Shoewu, O., Olaniyi, O. M., and Lawson, A. (2011). Embedded Computer-Based Lecture Attendance Management System. *African Journal of Computing and ICT*.4(3) P 27-36.
- Smart Card Alliance (2012). Now Security Technology Alliance: a Handbook on Identity Management Systems Comparison. <http://www.securetechalliance.org>.
- Terri, M. (2014). Smart ID Cards For Education ID Card Systems Advantage, Inc.htm
- Williams, K. (2010). The History of Identification Cards. November 14, 2011, from <http://ezinearticles.com/?The--History--of--Identification--Cards&id=3765530> pp 25-26.
- Xavier, L. (2017). Biometrics- the ID system of the future. Biometric identification, Communication. ACM, 43: 90-98.

Author(s)

1

Souley Boukhari

He is a distinguished Computer Science professor at Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University (ATBU) in Bauchi, Nigeria. He boasts an extensive publication record in reputable local and international journals and has actively participated in numerous conferences, both at the local and international levels. Sule's significant contributions to the field of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) underscore his commitment to advancing knowledge and expertise in the domain.

2

Amatullah Yahaya Aliyu

She is a faculty member in the Computer Science department at Federal Polytechnic, Bauchi. She earned her first and second degree (in Computer Science) from A.T.B.U respectively, followed by a Postgraduate Diploma in Education (P.G.D.E) from NTI, Kaduna. Currently pursuing a Ph.D. in Computer Science at A.T.B.U, Bauchi, she also holds a certification in Oracle Foundation, Database Design, and Programming with SQL.

Her primary research interests center around system/cyber security, software development, and data analysis.